

SCIANCE

D6.3

**AI in Science
Working Group
Terms of Reference**

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Abstract

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The Terms of Reference for the AI in Science Working Groups (AISWGs) define the objectives, structure, roles and responsibilities, and operational modalities of the working groups covering five scientific pilot areas and five cross-cutting AI-related topics. The Terms of Reference establish the framework for expert selection, including the criteria and open call for expression of interest through which experts from the European scientific and AI communities will be selected. The Terms of Reference also specify the expected contributions, confidentiality obligations, and duration of the AISWGs. The AISWGs will serve as dynamic communities of practice, mobilising domain scientists, AI researchers, industry experts, and Open Science advocates to co-create research and innovation priorities and infrastructure upgrade scenarios for the AI in Science Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). The annex provides the template for the Call for Expression of Interest.

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Terminology / Acronyms

AISWG	AI in Science Working Groups
RAISE	Resource for AI Science in Europe
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

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SCIANCE Project

The [SCIANCE](#) project is a European coordination initiative establishing the foundations for the [Resource for AI Science in Europe](#) (RAISE). The project promotes interdisciplinary collaboration to integrate AI into scientific research by enabling streamlined access to trustworthy data repositories, computing resources, and research infrastructures across Europe. Bringing together leading research infrastructures, scientific organisations, and AI centres of excellence, SCIANCE develops a Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) through an iterative co-creation process.

Building on a comprehensive AI-in-science landscape analysis, the SRIA identifies long-term research challenges where AI can accelerate discovery and defines cross-domain AI research and innovation priorities, focusing on open, trustworthy, and frugal AI methods for science. A roadmap for infrastructure upgrades and cooperation mechanisms supports its implementation, translating scientific research and innovation priorities into coordinated action. To consolidate the European AI-in-science ecosystem, SCIANCE pilots the RAISE Secretariat, supported by the RAISE Digital Hub, community-building events at annual AIS Summits, and the RAISE Academy, providing a continuous framework for engagement, capacity building, knowledge sharing, and cross-domain collaborations.

By combining scientific domain expertise with AI research and infrastructure knowledge, SCIANCE delivers robust, evidence-based guidance that is scientifically credible and strategically aligned with European Commission objectives, laying the foundations for future collaborative, AI-enabled science in Europe.

1 Scope and Objectives

1.1 Objective

The AI in Science Working Groups (AISWG) are established to mobilise the AI in science community and support the development of the AI in Science Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA). The AISWGs will contribute expert knowledge and strategic guidance to the identification and validation of AI in science research and innovation priorities in Europe and the required infrastructure upgrade scenarios and cooperation mechanisms for their implementation. The AISWG experts will be mobilised throughout the SRIA co-creation process and the follow-up validation, community consultation and strategic alignment phases.

1.2 Scope

10 thematic AISWGs are established, focusing on scientific pilot areas and cross-cutting AI-related topics. Each AISWG will be co-chaired by a SCIANCE consortium member with relevant expertise and one expert appointed from the AISWG members by the SCIANCE consortium. In cases where a working group covers multiple disciplines, an additional SCIANCE co-chair may be appointed to ensure adequate disciplinary coverage.

AI in Science Working Groups		
Working Group	Scope	SCIANCE co-chair(s)
Astronomy and Fundamental Physics	Research in astronomy and fundamental physics, domain-specific AI applications and data science, HPC and AI infrastructures, research infrastructures (CERN, SKA, LOFAR)	Manchester University and Nikhef
Materials Science	Research in materials science, domain-specific AI applications and data science, HPC and AI infrastructures, research infrastructures (CERIC-ERIC, ESRF, ILL, NOMAD)	Constructor University
Life Sciences	Research in life science, ethical, legal and societal implications (ELSI) for life science data, domain-specific AI applications and data science, HPC and AI infrastructures, research infrastructures	Euro-BiolImaging
Earth Sciences	Research in climate science, agriculture, land use, water resources, ecosystems, biodiversity and urban studies, Earth observation systems, domain-specific AI applications and data science, HPC and AI infrastructures, research infrastructures	UT-ITC
Social Sciences and Humanities	Research in social sciences and humanities, domain specific AI applications and data science, HPC and AI infrastructures, research infrastructures (heritage, health, data archives, arts and humanities)	CNR-ISTI
AI Research and Experimental Design	Autonomous laboratories, high-throughput experimentation, physics-informed and hybrid AI models, LLMs and NLP for science, AI co-scientist, lab and workflow automation, interdisciplinary AI model development and data standards, AI skills development	DFKI
Data Science and Advanced Analytics	Data governance and lifecycle management, semantic interoperability, data quality and preparation for AI, scalable and distributed data engineering, advanced analytics, data visualisation, synthetic data generation, metadata and open research libraries	BDVA
Open Science and Trustworthy AI	Open and trustworthy AI for scientific research, integrity and reproducibility, open science policy, legal and IPR frameworks (AI Act, GDPR), data protection, privacy and ethic, data-sharing regulations	OpenAIRE
AI and Computing Infrastructures	HPC, AI Factories, EOSC ecosystems, scholarly knowledge graphs, data labs integrated with AI infrastructures, research software, operational coordination of research and AI infrastructures, infrastructure policy and governance, ESFRI infrastructures	EGI
Industry, Innovation and Frugal AI	AI innovations for scientific research, AI-enabled laboratory systems and workflows, AI Factories across pilot areas, cloud providers for research, GenAI for science, AI industry technology developments, frugal and resource-efficient AI	HUN-REN SZTAKI

1.3 Membership

The AISWGs will bring together scientific and AI researchers, industry experts, Open Science advocates, representatives from relevant European initiatives and infrastructures, and citizen scientists. Participation to the AISWG is on a voluntary basis.

The AISWG members are selected through an open Call for Expression of Interest (CEoI) published on the SCIANCE website (www.sciance.eu) and circulated via scientific societies and European AI networks. Self-nomination and third-party nomination are both accepted.

The detailed scope and composition of each AISWG is informed by the state-of-the-art review and landscape analysis conducted by the SCIANCE project. The specific expertise sought for each working group will be finalised before the evaluation of applications and selection of experts in May 2026.

2 Roles and Responsibilities

2.1 AISWG Members

AISWG members will:

- provide expert-level contributions to the AI in Science SRIA
- participate in interdisciplinary workshops with other AISWG members to identify AI in science and AI for science research and innovation priorities and infrastructure upgrade requirements
- participate in AISWG meetings to build consensus, review projects outputs and provide feedback
- provide additional inputs, insights, resources and data if necessary
- support dissemination and uptake by sharing selected SCIANCE outputs, consultation opportunities and results within their own communities, networks, infrastructures or initiatives where appropriate
- promote transparency and cross-fertilisation across scientific domains and AI-related topics

2.2 AISWG Co-Chairs

In addition to the responsibilities of members, the co-chairs will:

- facilitate strategic discussions and contributions of the AISWG
- coordinate with other AISWG co-chairs to align recommendations on cross-cutting topics

2.3 RAISE Secretariat

The RAISE Secretariat will support AISWG activities throughout the project by facilitating meeting organisation and access to relevant documentation, monitoring balanced representation and distribution of effort, and ensuring continuity of engagement across working groups. This includes supporting documentation, traceability of inputs, access to relevant digital resources, and coordination with the SCIANCE consortium.

3 Meetings and Workshops

3.1 Co-creation Workshops

The SCIANCE project will organise a series of co-creation workshops to identify research and innovation priorities, interdisciplinary collaboration opportunities, and infrastructure gaps, and to define upgrade requirements and cooperation mechanisms. Workshops involve experts from different AISWGs to facilitate interdisciplinary discussion and are co-located with relevant scientific conferences and infrastructure events where feasible.

Each AISWG expert is expected to participate in at least one in-person workshop over the course of the project. The SCIANCE project will support travel expenses for workshop participants, within the allocated project budget.

3.2 Online Meetings

AISWGs meet online at least twice a year and additionally on a need-basis when specific project outputs require review, feedback or consensus-building. Asynchronous feedback through shared documents and the RAISE Digital Hub Forum may be used to reduce meeting burden.

In-person participation at relevant conferences and the annual AI in Science Summits is encouraged where feasible.

4 Selection Process

4.1 Call for Expression of Interest

Experts are invited to express their interest via a dedicated call for expression of interest.

Applications are sought from individuals with expertise in one or more of the following areas:

- Scientific research in the areas covered by the AISWGs
- AI methods for scientific discovery, experimental design and research workflows, data sciences
- Scientific research infrastructures, dataspace, AI and computing infrastructures
- Open Science, citizen science, trustworthy and frugal AI
- AI industry, innovation and technology developments

Self-nomination or nomination by a third party will be permitted.

4.2 Selection Criteria

All applications will be assessed by an evaluation panel from the SCIANCE consortium partners with relevant expertise in the working group topics. The selection process aims to avoid concentration of influence and ensure broad, inclusive participation. An anonymised summary of selection outcomes will be published to ensure openness and accountability.

The selection of AISWG experts will be based on the following set of publicly available criteria:

- **Expertise:** relevant expertise in one or more domains pertinent to the AISWG scope, and complementarity with the overall expertise covered in the working group based on the inputs from the state-of-the-art reviews and landscape analysis.
- **Contribution:** availability to participate in-person workshops, working groups meetings, provide additional asynchronous contributions, and review of the AI in science SRIA.
- **Diversity:** balanced representation across disciplines, EU Member States and Associated Countries, career stages and gender.
- **Coverage:** representation across diverse stakeholder communities, including academia, industry, research infrastructures, civil society and public bodies, assessed at the level of overall group composition.

5 Confidentiality and Data Protection

AISWG members will treat all non-public documents, draft materials and discussions as confidential. Personal data will be processed in accordance with applicable EU and national legislation. Where Digital Hub restricted spaces are used, access will be managed according to confidentiality, access-control and data-protection rules.

The composition of the AISWG will be publicly available, and contribution from the AISWG experts will be acknowledged in the SRIA, roadmap and other project documents.

6 Duration

The AISWGs will operate until the end of the SCIANCE project, expected in May 2028.

Members may withdraw by written notice. The consortium may replace members where necessary to maintain continuity of engagement throughout the project.

7 Governance and Decision-making

The AISWGs act in an advisory capacity.

All decisions relating to project deliverables remain the responsibility of the SCIANCE consortium. AISWG consensus will be sought whenever possible, and dissenting views may be recorded when relevant.